

AUTHOR'S INDIVIDUAL APPROACH TO THE FATES OF HEROES IN THE XX TH CENTURY ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERATURE

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After the complete establishment of the Soviet rule, literary criticism became one of the main weapons to publicize benefits of the Communist Party. All scientific schools except the Marxist method were heavily labelled as “bourgeois reaction.” In the 1920s–1930s, the interpretations based on the Marxist-Leninist ideology destroyed a number of writers’ lives who were representatives of “Jadids,” “nationalists,” and “petit bourgeois” and led them into trouble. In the 1940s, the investigations concerning the analysis of the problems of spiritual depiction were also seriously criticized as aesthetic-cosmopolitanism. Even aesthetic thoughts of literature such as beauty, tragedy, spiritual perfectness, and lowliness were studied from the point of communist ideology. Those objects based on the policy of “might makes right” were brought to create writings in decided shapes and to smother free creativity. As a result, schematism, utopian ideas of false humanism, and a tendency to analyze from the point of view of the social classes were developed in literary works. After 1990, with a change of political regime, literary politics also remained in the bottom of history with its own creator—colonial system, and a huge vacuum appeared between the old and new periods of Uzbek literary criticism. Bound to the old approaches, some Uzbek scholars openly continued to follow the old methodological tendencies, while others waited for a “prepared methodological model” for the new Uzbek literary process. In the next stage of literary criticism, the independence period, a basic reinventing process appeared in literary thought and in literary works, which can be termed “modern.” It became clear that it was impossible to understand and realize the essence of a new literary process through old literary criteria, although each period had its own leading views. Even for the leaders of Uzbek literary criticism, it was hard to accept the new literary phenomenon. As a result, uncompromising struggles between new and old methodological approaches appeared from 1995 to the 2000s. In the current article, I will systematically analyze the duration of the study of the 20th century Uzbek literature. I will identify specific features of each period and show how Soviet realism impacted Uzbek literary criticism. In addition, I will reveal the main essence of paradoxical approaches in reinvented literary art, and show

fundamental factors of conflicts in creating a new tendency of methodology of Uzbek literary criticism in the transitional period.

After the complete establishment of the Soviet rule, literary criticism became one of the main weapons to publicize benefits of the Communist Party. All scientific schools except the Marxist method were heavily labelled as “bourgeois reaction.” In the 1920s–1930s, the interpretations based on the Marxist-Leninist ideology destroyed a number of writers’ lives who were representatives of “Jadids,” “nationalists,” and “petit bourgeois” and led them into trouble. In the 1940s, the investigations concerning the analysis of the problems of spiritual depiction were also seriously criticized as aesthetic-cosmopolitanism. Even aesthetic thoughts of literature such as beauty, tragedy, spiritual perfectness, and lowliness were studied from the point of communist ideology. Those objects based on the policy of “might makes right” were brought to create writings in decided shapes and to smother free creativity. As a result, schematism, utopian ideas of false humanism, and a tendency to analyze from the point of view of the social classes were developed in literary works. Objectiveness and possibilities of literary critics in analysis were limited, and criticism was declared as the main power of the Communist Party. Literature and literary critics became one focal point of the ideological struggle.¹ However, it is important to emphasize that some literary critics such as Ozod Sharaffidinov and Matyoqub Qo‘shjonov carried out important research related to the 20th century literature, which managed to renew literary critical ideas and critical thought from 1960 to 1985. Yet, these kinds of investigations were not enough to pressure vulgar socialist methods and create a new methodology of Uzbek literature in that period. After 1990, with a change of political regime, literary politics also remained in the bottom of history with its own creator—colonial system, and a huge vacuum appeared between the old and new periods of Uzbek literary criticism. Bound to the old approaches, some Uzbek scholars openly continued to follow the old methodological tendencies, while others waited for a “prepared methodological model” for the new Uzbek literary process. In the next stage of literary criticism, the independence period, a basic reinventing process appeared in literary thought and in literary works, which can be termed “modern.” It became clear that it was impossible to understand and realize the essence of a new literary process through old literary criteria, although each period had its own leading views. Even for the leaders of Uzbek literary criticism, it was hard to accept the new literary phenomenon. As a result, uncompromising struggles between new and old methodological

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In exploring the individual approach to the fates of heroes in 20th-century English and Uzbek literature, it's fascinating to consider the diverse cultural, historical, and artistic contexts that shaped the portrayal of characters and their destinies in these literary traditions.

English Literature

In 20th-century English literature, there was a significant evolution in the depiction of heroes and their fates, reflecting the upheavals, challenges, and changing societal norms of the era. Here are a few notable trends and approaches:

Modernist and Postmodernist Experiments

- Many English literary figures of the 20th century, especially in the modernist and postmodernist movements, presented heroes with complex and often enigmatic destinies. Writers such as James Joyce, Virginia Woolf, and T.S. Eliot emphasized the fragmented nature of human experience and consciousness, depicting heroes who often struggled with existential crises and fragmented identities.

Individual and Psychological Realism

- Writers like D.H. Lawrence and Virginia Woolf delved into the inner lives of their characters, presenting heroes whose fates were deeply intertwined with their psychological and emotional journeys. These authors offered insight into the intricate personal worlds of their protagonists, often revealing the impact of societal changes and psychological turmoil on the individual.

Exploration of Social and Political Forces

- Some English authors, including George Orwell and Aldous Huxley, used their works to explore the impact of social, political, and technological forces on the fates of their heroes. In dystopian and speculative fiction, characters faced the daunting challenges of oppressive societies, dehumanizing technology, and the erosion of individual agency.

Uzbek Literature

In 20th-century Uzbek literature, the depiction of heroes and their fates was influenced by the nation's complex history, cultural traditions, and the struggle for identity and independence. Here are some significant aspects of the Uzbek literary tradition:

Folklore and National Identity

- Uzbek literature often drew from rich folklore, epic tales, and historical narratives, presenting heroes deeply rooted in the traditions and values of Uzbek society. The fates of these heroes were often entwined with the preservation of cultural and national identity, facing obstacles imposed by external forces and historical upheavals.

Soviet Influence and Social Realism

- During the Soviet era, Uzbek literature underwent a period of social realism, emphasizing heroes who were often portrayed as collective figures, representing the aspirations and challenges of the working class and peasantry. Their fates were interwoven with the broader social and political dynamics of the time, reflecting the impacts of collectivization, industrialization, and the quest for social equality.

Exploration of Personal and National Struggles

- Modern Uzbek literature often grappled with the individual and national struggles of characters, reflecting the complexities of societal transformation, cultural revival, and the quest for self-determination. Heroes in these works often faced the tensions between tradition and modernity, personal desires and societal expectations, as well as the search for meaning in a changing world.

In both English and Uzbek literature, the individual approach to the fates of heroes in the 20th century reflects a dynamic interplay of cultural, historical, and artistic influences. The portrayal of heroes and their destinies serves as a mirror to the complexities of human experience, societal transformations, and the quest for identity and meaning.

In the 1980s and 1990s the re-studying of Uzbek Soviet literature was formed by the discussions, including denial and confirmation. A group of literary critics and scholars would try to judge the works of M. T. Oybek, A. Qahhor, and G. G'ulom based on the communist motives in their works, while others would try to justify them, considering that they were made to write such "modern" works under the requirements of the hegemon ideology. Both sides tried to bring scientific facts to prove their opinions. Because of the inability to avoid the thinking shaped under the sixty-year utopian ideas, and to understand changes happening in the social life and literary study, some scholars had to remain in a neutral position

or be out of renewing the literary process. In the early years of independence, the question “What should be the literature of the period of independence” was raised at the political level. A group of literary critics and writers created new methodological foundations of literature and literary criticism of independence. The study of literature from the point of view of an ideology of independence (patriotism, religious tolerance, respect for national values, etc.) as well as the attempt to discover the ideas of national identity from Uzbek Soviet literature increased from 1995 through to the 2000s. From the 2000s a new, systematic, and structural approach which mostly focused on pragmatic functions of literature appeared in the national criticism. However, these new methods have not been developed. In the 2000s there appeared new uncompromising struggles between realists and modernists on whether Uzbek literature needs modernism and postmodernism. Although the representatives of traditional literature strictly rejected modernism as an imitation of Western literature, today it became one of the main directions of modern Uzbek literary art. To put it more precisely, while modernism was only originally expressed in poetry in the beginning of the 21st century, a number of novels and short stories are written by Uzbek writers in the way of modernism at present. Some critics tried to prove that literature, including Uzbek, cannot be out of changes on a global scale, and to be more dispassionate in accepting modernism and postmodernism since it is not a simple phenomenon.

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